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Where is Russian higher education? The spatial imaginaries and realities of internationalization policy

Svetlana Shenderova^{a,*}, Jeremy Morris^b, Giorgio Comai^c^a University of Helsinki, Faculty of Arts, Aleksanteri Institute, Metsätalo, Unioninkatu 40, P.O. Box 24, FI-00014 Helsinki, Finland^b Aarhus University, School of Culture and Society, Denmark^c OBC Transeuropa, Centro per la Cooperazione Internazionale, Italy

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ABSTRACT

The article considers how and at which recent historical and political junctures documents, experts and academics frame the internationalization of Russian higher education (HE) in the course of neoliberal reforms. Asking how new boundaries for Russian HE have re-emerged, re-imaged and aligned with internationalization policy, we explore whether the current trend of isolation for Russian HE is realistic. For this purpose, we examine the regional spaces and spatial imaginaries of Russian HE, investigate how and why they contradict with the principles and particularly, implementation of internationalization policy. We develop the concept of 'shadows in internationalization', exploring how a privileged internationalization, understood as a set of deliberately built decision-making mechanisms to provide the rent extraction for policy insiders, hinders quality and equity in Russian HE and its regional spaces outside. We outline how and why Russia's leadership have incorporated quantitative evaluation criteria for internationalization policy amidst neoliberal reforms, and juxtapose them with implementation realities. In doing so, we focus on internationalization activities which Russian universities are obliged to develop in HE and dynamics of related publications of Russia-affiliated scholars to reveal their alignment with the spatial imaginaries. We conclude that implementation of internationalization policy based on Western criteria, coupled with monopolisation of privileges and a traditional rigidity of university governance, contradict spatial imaginaries of a globalising and internationalising of Russian HE in prioritised regional spaces and worldwide. We argue that this contradiction continues to undermine the quality and cohesion of national and regional spaces of Russian higher education from inside.

1. Introduction

The global and regional positioning of Russian higher education (HE) has been reimagined several times since the collapse of the USSR and the onset of neoliberal reforms focused on internationalization. The article considers how and where internationalized Russian HE as a globally and regionally-identifiable system is understood and imagined in policy documents, public speeches of

Abbreviations: CPSU, Communist Party of the Soviet Union; GoR, Government of Russia; HE, higher education; MFA, Ministry of Foreign Affairs; MOOCs, Massive Open Online Courses; MoSHE, Ministry of Science and Higher Education; PA, Presidential Administration; PoR, President of Russia.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: svetlana.shenderova@helsinki.fi (S. Shenderova), jmorris@cas.au.dk (J. Morris), giorgio.comai@cci.tn.it (G. Comai).

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Russia's leaders, and publications of experts and academics. For this purpose, we analyse policy documents related national security, foreign affairs and internationalization of HE. We also cover relevant public speeches of the President of Russia (PoR), representatives of his Executive Office also known as Presidential Administration (PA), Government of Russia (GoR), Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA), and the Ministry of HE and Science (MoSHE). These are the key stakeholders of Russia's internationalization policy who use the most influential Russian media to send their messages to each other, highly ranked officials, politicians and experts, for further policy development. These stakeholders use a set of Presidential Decrees, Government Directives, and Ministerial orders to establish the policy aims. However, they avoid defining the sum of internationalization policy or strategy of Russia's HE in a single document, unlike in neighbouring Norway (KD, 2021) or Finland (OKM, 2017).

In addition, key stakeholders delegate the task of rationalizing policy aims to a few higher education institutions (HEIs) and quasi-independent think tanks. The specificity of Russian HE is that the vast majority of Russian universities, currently 818, have much lesser (if any) salience in policy development (Shenderova, 2025). In addition, we consider publications by Russia-affiliated authors whom we include as examples of an epistemic community academics and experts who developed or studied Russia's policy in foreign affairs and internationalization of HE. We particularly focus on authors who have permanently or temporarily been affiliated with those Russian HE institutions (HEIs) which have a mandate for policy development in foreign affairs and internationalization of HE given by the President, Government, and the MFA.

The aforementioned documents, speeches and literature have determined the permissible boundaries of the positioning discourses on Russian HE globally and regionally. These include the watchwords and mantras related to various stages of HE reforms. These reforms often are represented as 'neoliberal' due to the introduction of fee-based education in state and private universities (Smolentseva, 2017), performance-based funding, and the emergence of specially-funded elite segment of so-called *leading universities* (Kuzminov & Yudkevich, 2022). Partial exemption of these universities from regulative limitations is presented as extension of university autonomy and academic freedom in Russia (Volkov, Kuzminov & Yudkevich, 2023).

The internationalization of HE has been a linchpin of post-socialist reforms in Russia. This epitomized a desire of Russian elites to overcome their isolation from the globally recognised leaders of the knowledge-based economy (Shenderova et al., 2023). Restoring capitalism in the 1990s, Russia turned the macro-focus of international HE cooperation from socialist and developing countries to the Global North embodied by Western Europe, or wider, 'the West'.¹ However, this reorientated had precedents even in the recent past: the USSR had suspended all HE cooperation with China in 1960s-1980s and concentrated on socialist Eastern Europe and developing countries in Africa, Middle East and Southeast Asia.

The fall of the Iron Curtain opened up Russian HE for Western international education agencies, universities and funding programmes (Burquel et al., 2014). EU and European states funding played a significant role in neoliberal reforms in Russian HE. However, these reforms were poorly aligned with each other (Shenderova et al., 2023). Furthermore, new government regulation including introduction of the Federal State Educational Standards (FSES)² attempted to check falling standards in the quality of education but also hindered flexibility of the degree programmes in Russian universities. Thus, new opportunities for knowledge exchange and a chaotic rise of international contacts did not fully impact the everyday life of Russian universities. The rocketing number of fee-based students became a main source for university survival in the course of the state funding decline (Shenderova, 2011).

In the 2000s, Russia continued neoliberal reforms; a series of national projects funded the edifice of an internationally-oriented façade for HE system. These reforms aligned with global trends including the importance of international experts and ranking agencies, preferential selection of universities for the state support, targeted funding, and expansion of performance-based quantitative indicators increased university accountability (Trow, 2007; Gornitzka & Maassen, 2011; Kwiek, 2013; Hazelkorn, 2016; Maassen et al., 2017; Kivistö et al., 2024). In Russia, reforms often boiled down to so-called 'optimization', meaning a significant reduction of state funding for HEIs and student places financed by the federal budget. The total number of HEIs in Russia decreased from 1000 in 2013 to 818 in 2024. At the university level, this led to a decrease and fragmentation of academic positions with teaching workload of frequently over 900 contact hours per academic (Ustyuzhantseva et al., 2020). University top-managers accumulated the tuition fees from increased number of fee-based students spending this income on their sole discretion (Shenderova, 2011).

The growth of state funding for internationalization gave a rise to government and quasi-independent agencies. They administered the state programmes which funded internationalization; Russian universities are accountable to these agencies, not to the society. Both universities and the state apparatus have avoided building democratic institutions at sectoral and university level (Shenderova et al., 2024). New international actors of internationalization policy have been indifferent to multiple conflicts of interests (Kangas et al., 2023; Chirikov, 2023). All this contributed to shaping and legitimizing neoliberal authoritarian regime in Russia (Forrat, 2016; Morris, 2021). Russia's leadership has continued internationally focused performance-based HE reforms since making a new about turn of international priorities when their long-term partners in the Global North countries suspended cooperation due to Russia's

¹ The 'West' is a term used in Russia since imperial times with adding adjectives 'rotten' or 'enlightened' depending on the speakers' political preferences. Currently, Russia's leadership prefer the conspiracy-sound term 'collective West' with particular selection of 'Anglo-Saxon countries' within.

² The degrees are recognised in Russia only if they comply with the Federal State Educational Standards (FSES). Russian universities are able to develop their degrees within the list of study areas determined by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education. FSES determine each field of study within which the universities are able to develop the degrees, a structure of each degree programme and its length of study. The procedures of state licensing, state accreditation and state monitoring map compliance of each degree programme with the FSES requirements, and as such these are quality assurance mechanisms in Russian higher education. Only state accredited degree programmes provide a deferment from obligatory military service by conscription for male students during the length of study.

annexation of Crimea in 2014 and full-scale invasion to Ukraine in 2022 (Shenderova, 2025). Currently, Russian universities build new partnership in the Global South countries.

Thus, in the first quarter of 21st century internationalization policy has been a part of neoliberal reforms in Russian HE albeit in an environment of changing global macro-focuses under an impact of geopolitical shifts. Table 1 gives a clue for understanding interplay for the declared goals of authoritarian regime, neoliberal reforms, and macro-focuses of internationalization policy. Table 1 outlines the mantras and buzzwords used on various stages of the reforms through internationalization.

Thus, in the mid-2010, Russia's leadership formally admitted the internationalization of HE as 'the intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension unto the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education, in order to enhance the quality of education and research for all' (de Wit et al., 2015: 281). Policy criteria, evaluation and implementation of internationalization policy have relied on neoliberal tools. The declared care of 'traditional Russian spiritual and moral values' (PoR, 2022) have not prevented Russian authorities from using the tools developed under the impact of transnational, in particular, Anglo-centric approaches (Mäkinen, 2021), for the sake of global competitiveness of Russian HE (Gruening, 2001; Smolentseva, 2017:1100; Chirikov & Fedyukin, 2021: 237). Since the launch of 'competitiveness enhancement' stage of reforms, a particular attention has focused on the Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) world university ranking (Shenderova, 2018a; Chirikov, 2023) based on calculation of Scopus indexed publications cited per faculty (QS, 2024; Elsevier, 2024) and numbers of international students and academics (Volkov, Kuzminov & Yudkevich, 2023). Another world university ranking (WUR), Times Higher Education (THE), is also in the focus (Gershman et al., 2025)

Current reforms with a mantra of 'technological sovereignty' aim to facilitate Russia's entry into the league of the ten globally-leading countries in the volume of research and development (PoR, 2024b). However, Russia's leadership looks at the success of national HE through the lenses of WURs mostly developed outside the country. Two of them (QS and THE) are hosted in the UK, currently considered as an 'aggressive to Russia' (TASS, 2025a), and one in China (Academic Ranking of World Universities, ARWU). The only domestic ranking 'Three university missions' (MosiUR) is based on global bibliometric databases including Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) (Rossiyskaya Gazeta, 2022; RUR, 2023).

Thus, since the mass expansion of Russian HE in 1960s, its reforms a) have changed their macro-focus of international cooperation radically three times; b) have jumped from socialist administration to neoliberal approach through internationalization maintaining traditions of the former. Therefore, despite the formal adoption of internationalization in accordance with abovementioned definition and declaration of split with the West, Russia considers internationalization of HE as boosting the numbers of international students, academics, and publications in 'highly-ranked international journals' (Gershman et al., 2025: 122). This peculiar combination raises a set of questions overlooked in the literature.

Firstly, we ask where is Russian HE spatially, outlining the boundaries of its regional and global expansion. Secondly, we inquire how Russian politicum and academia imagine the boundaries of Russian HE. Thirdly, we seek how these imaginaries impact on Russia's internationalization policy, its main indicators and the realities of implementation showing the positions of Russian HE in prioritised regions and globally.

Answering these questions, we draw upon the notions of the regional spaces (Leskina & Sabzalieva, 2021; Chankseliani & Sopromadze, 2023) and spatial imaginaries (Brooks & Rensimer, 2024). We consider regional spaces of Russian HE as supranational

Table 1
Neoliberal reforms of Russian HE in first quarter of 21st century.

Years	Mantra and definition	Rationale	Main criteria	Macro-focus of international cooperation	Main state programme
2005 –2010	'Innovative development' of Russian leading universities to provide quality of education relevant to modern demands (PoR, 2006)	Modernisation of national economy to make it competitive globally	Numbers of innovative educational programmes in collaboration with international partners Numbers of foreign equipment purchases Numbers of employees visited abroad Numbers of invited international academics	Global North	Priority National Project 'Education'
2012 –2020	'Competitiveness enhancement' is a plan of measures to provide development of leading universities amongst the leading world scientific-educational centres (PoR, 2012)	Training of qualified specialists taking into account the requirements of the innovative economy	5 Russian universities in a first hundred of the leading world universities in accordance with a world university ranking	Global North	5–100 Russian Academic Excellence Project
2022 - present	'Technological sovereignty' is a presence in a country of critical and cross-cutting technologies for sustainable achievement of national development goals and implementation of national interests (PoR, 2022c; GoR, 2023).	Strengthening national security to defend the national interests of Russia under conditions of external pressure	Russia amidst ten leading countries as providers research and development	Global South	Priority 2030 Programme

alliances which transcend national boundaries, aim at fostering cross-border collaboration and integration, and prioritized by Russia's policy documents. We uncover and examine the spatial boundaries of these regional spaces and their permeability to understand the impact of external sanctions and internal securitization which currently serve to isolate Russian HE.

The concept of spatial imaginaries of HE is understood here as socially held stories with their own agency that constitute particular ways of discussing the place of Russian HE in different regional spaces. Following [Rensimer and Brooks \(2024\)](#), we explore to what extent the spatial imaginaries of Russian HE correspond with the practices of internationalization developed through the interaction of the stakeholders involved in policy making and implementation. We analyse the discursive patterns of spatial imaginaries, their validity as the strategic policy tools, their impact on internationalization policy, and compare them with policy implementation results. In so doing, we take into account that the abovementioned specifics of Russia, where key policy stakeholders do not involve a majority of Russian universities in shaping the discourse, collective imagination, and policy development.

Hard boundaries in HE seem to be the result of the turn to 'sovereignty' in Russian internationalization policy, along with the abovementioned sanctions ([Mäkinen, 2024](#); [Shenderova, 2025](#)). However, we show Russian policy documents and authors have always prioritized the Global North, and particularly, Western Europe, as a benchmark for national HE.

The article is divided into the following sections. Firstly, we discuss how geopolitical challenges and policy documents have influenced on regional spaces of Russian HE and their geographical boundaries. We particularly focus on permeability of these boundaries in the West, South and East. Then we unveil the spatial imaginaries of Russian HE in relation to these regional spaces and to the globe. In addition, we show an internal contradiction within the spatial imaginaries: they simultaneously request Russian universities to prioritize highly-ranked well-known partners and develop activities in the regional spaces where local universities have much more modest research capacity.

Further, we show how and why implementation of internationalization policy has contradicted the spatial imaginaries of Russian HE. We argue that internationalization policy facilitated the concentration of academic privileges and funding within a narrow circle of universities. Developing the concept of shadows in internationalization ([Shenderova et al., 2024](#)), we argue that exclusive internationalization as an aspect of academic privilege, generated the dark-side effects which hinder quality and equity in Russian HE and its regional spaces outside. We unveil that privileged internationalization is a result of revival the Soviet traditions and deliberate efforts of Russian and international policy stakeholders who focused more on quantitative criteria than on quality international education for all.

Subsequently, we analyse how Russian universities achieve the requested goals implementing internationalization activities in HE. We show how policy implementation contradicts with the spatial imaginaries of Russian HE and give rise to forms of neocoloniality. Then, we evaluate to what extent internationalizing Russian universities follow the global trend of increase publications in the internationalization of HE as a field of study. For this purpose, we review internationalization the dynamics of global and Russia-affiliated publications indexed by international databases. This reveals how the interest of Russia-affiliated academics to develop and study internationalization was mainly dependent on scholars' following policy trends, and we question how sustainable this interest is. We particularly focus on the dynamics of publications written by Russia-affiliated authors and indexed in the Q1 and Q2 segments of the WoS and Scopus because Russia's leadership have requested their growth from Russian universities.

We conclude that Russian state and academia imagine national HE as globally competitive, attractive and unique. However, in implementing these imaginaries through internationalization policy, they recognise only very rough Western quantitative measures of output, equating an increase with the success of internationalization. This is compounded by domestic traditions of concentrating privileges in a few universities, data extraction instead of quality increase at the system level, and a lack of interest in grassroots feedback and involvement of all Russian universities in policy development. Thus, an absence of university community amongst the policy stakeholders devalues spatial imaginaries on Russian HE from a strategic tool to a rhetoric construction. The neoliberal authoritarian reforms do not only align with the declared imaginaries on global impact and leading role of Russian HE in prioritized regional spaces. They undermine the cohesion of research and HE area within the country.

2. Methods

The paper draws upon an analysis of relevant policy documents, public speeches, statistics, websites of all associations developed fostering cross-border HE cooperation and prioritised in Russia's policy documents. The scope of publications comprises the contributions of Russia-affiliated authors involved in policy development and justification in the course of their affiliation with the universities and think-tanks mandated for these purposes by the President, Government, MFA and MoSHE.

The policy document analysis is based on a set of Presidential decrees, Government directives and Ministerial orders, outlined the principles and priorities of Russia's policy in foreign affairs, security, science and HE; the main state programmes supported internationalization and their detail analysis in a series of relevant publications. We highlight the public claims of the President including the Addresses to the Federal Assembly; representatives of PA, Government, MoSHE, MFA, and Russian Union of Rectors (RUR) mentioned at their official websites, and their statements recorded by leading state media of Russia (TASS, Interfax, Rossiyskaya Gazeta, AIF, and RIA Novosti).

We also include into consideration the documents and data found at the websites of the relevant associations which Russian policy document prioritized for internationalization of HE and foreign affairs in the [Table 2](#).

We add the data related to particular internationalization activities, found at the websites of MoSHE, universities, and think tanks responsible for these activities as umbrella organizations along with policy development in foreign affairs, listed in the [Table 3](#) and [Table 4](#). Our analysis of Russia-affiliated publications considered internationalization of HE and spatial positioning of Russia includes pieces by authors who have been affiliated with these organizations permanently or temporarily in 2000–2025 including membership in international advisory and supervisory bodies.

Table 2

List of associations prioritised by Russia's foreign and internationalization policies in 1990s -mid-2020s.

Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS)
Eurasian Economic Union (EEU)
Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO)
Brazil, Russia India, China, South Africa (BRICS+)
European Higher Education Area (EHEA)

Table 3

List of universities involved in internationalization policy justification and development and their founders.

National Research University Higher School of Economics (HSE) – GoR
Lomonosov Moscow State University (MSU) - GoR
Moscow State Institute of International Relations of the MFA (MGIMO university)
Russian Academy of National Economy and Public Administration (RANEPA) under the President - PA, GoR
Russian People's Friendship University named after Patrice Lumumba (PFUR) - MoSHE
Saint-Petersburg State University (SPbSU) - GoR
Skolkovo Moscow School of Management (Skolkovo), private institution of additional professional education

Table 4

List of think tanks involved in policy development in foreign affairs and internationalization of HE.

Council on Foreign and Defense Policy (CFDP)
Russian International Affairs Council (RIAC)
Valdai Club

Our sources include the websites of universities specially funded for internationalization and intervention to WURs by the Government (Shenderova, 2018b). These are 21 universities supported by 5–100, two oldest universities of Russia (SPbSU established in 1724 and MSU established in 1755) specially funded for Russia's representation in the world since 2006, and RANEPA supported by the Government and PA for intervention to WURs since 2012 (see Table 5).

We also reviewed the websites of quality assurance agencies who accredited their collaborative degree programmes. Our scope of data includes authors' observations gathered for over 30 years of work in nine Russian, three European and three British universities, and also in the reviews of all Russian universities and their partners developed collaborative degrees with the European states including the UK.

In order to gauge the extent to which Russia-affiliated scholars respond to pressures for publishing articles and to reveal the dynamics of their research interest related to internationalization of HE as a mantra, we have conducted a bibliometric analysis in Western-hosted and developed scholarly databases, namely Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. These sources have been selected as the Russia's leadership forces universities to rely upon these databases for performance measurement. Taking into account the above-mentioned Government's focus on 'highly-ranked journals', we filter results in order to keep only articles published in Q1 and Q2-ranked journals.

To capture publications that explicitly focus on internationalization of HE, our analysis is based only on articles that match either of the following criteria: (1) the full string "internationali(s|z)ation of higher education" is present in either title or abstract; (2) the author-provided keywords include both "higher education" and "internationali(s|z)ation".

In order to differentiate publication dynamics that are specific to Russian academia from broader trends, we analyse data disaggregated by affiliation of the authors, offering a separate record for publications that have at least one author with a Russian affiliation. We apply the same criteria to WoS, Scopus, and OpenAlex" (Comai, 2025a–c)³. Thus, we observe consistent results specific to Russia in each of these sources. In spite of the relatively small number of relevant publications by Russia-based scholars identified through our approach, the fact that we observe the same trends using different sources, as well as by adjusting slightly selection criteria, confirms that these observations are not skewed by overreliance on a specific database.

3. Regional spaces of Russian HE and their spatial boundaries

The fall of the Iron Curtain opened Russian and Western HE to each other; Russia lost the interest to collaborate with the former partners in socialist bloc and non-aligned countries (Shenderova et al., 2023). An appearance of five new overlapping regional spaces (see Table 6) instead of socialist-oriented HE systems, forced politicians and academia to reimagine the place of Russian HE in the boundaries for Russia's HE expansion through cross-border HE initiatives.

The boundaries for Russian HE are open in the East and South. However, hopes to use the Soviet reputation (Interfax, 2017a), meet

³ On the usefulness of combining data retrieved from different bibliometric databases, see in particular Velez-Estevez et al. (2023). For an analysis of how OpenAlex compares to Scopus and WoS, see Culbert et al. (2025)

Table 5

List of Russian universities supported by the Government for intervention to WURs.

University, name	Status	Grounds and year since supported for internationalisation		
		Government support for Development Programme	5–100 2020	Priority 2030
St. Petersburg State University (SPbSU)	oldest university of Russia and particularly valuable object of national heritage	2006		
Moscow State University named after M.V. Lomonosov (MSU)	oldest university of Russia and particularly valuable object of national heritage	2006		
National Research University Higher School of Economics (HSE)	National research	2008	2013	2021
Siberian Federal University (SFU) (Krasnoyarsk)	Federal	2006	2015	2021
National University of Science and Technology MISiS (NUST MISiS) (Moscow)	National Research	2008	2013	2021
National Research Nuclear University MEPhI (Moscow)	National Research	2008	2013	2021
Immanuel Kant Baltic Federal University (BFU) (Kaliningrad)	Federal	2010	2015	2021
Far Eastern Federal University (FEFU) (Vladivostok)	Federal	2010	2013	2021
Kazan (Volga) Federal University (KFU) (Kazan)	Federal	2010	2013	2021
Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology (MIPT) (Moscow)	National Research	2009	2013	2021
Lobachevsky University (UNN) (Nizhny Novgorod)	National Research	2009	2013	2021
Novosibirsk State University (NSU) (Novosibirsk)	National Research	2009	2013	2021
Peoples' Friendship University of Russia (RUDN) (Moscow)		2011	2015	2021
Samara National Research University (SSAU) named after S.P. Korolev (Samara)	National Research	2010	2013	2021
Saint-Petersburg Electrotechnical University (LETI) (Saint Petersburg)	National Research	2011	2013	2021
Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University (SPbPU) (Saint Petersburg)	National Research	2010	2013	2021
Tomsk State University (TSU) (Tomsk)	National Research	2010	2013	2021
Tomsk Polytechnic University (TPU) (Tomsk)	National Research	2010	2013	2021
ITMO University (Saint Petersburg)	National Research	2010	2013	2021
Ural Federal University (UrFU) (Ekaterinburg)	National Research	2010	2013	2021
South Ural State University (SUSU) (Chelyabinsk)	National Research	2010	2013	2021
University of Tyumen (Tyumen)	National Research		2015	2021
First Moscow State Medical University (MSMU) (Moscow)			2015	2021
Russian Academy of National Economy and Public Administration under the President of Russian Federation (RANEPA)		2012		2021

Table 6

Regional spaces of Russian HE.

CIS, 1991 - present	SCO, 2001 – present	BRICS 2009 - present	EEU, 2015- present	EHEA, 2003 - present
Russia	Russia	Russia	Russia	Russia
Armenia	Belarus	Brazil	Armenia	Armenia
Azerbaijan	Kazakhstan	South Africa	Belarus	Azerbaijan
Belarus	Kyrgyzstan	Indonesia	Kazakhstan	Belarus
Kazakhstan	Tajikistan	Ethiopia	Kyrgyzstan	Kazakhstan
Kyrgyzstan	Uzbekistan	United Arab Emirates		Moldova
Moldova	Pakistan	China		27 EU member states
Tajikistan	China	India		Albania
Uzbekistan	India	Iran		Andorra
	Iran	Egypt		Bosnia and Herzegovina
				Georgia
				Holy See
				Montenegro
				North Macedonia
				San Marino
				Serbia
				Switzerland
				Türkiye
				Ukraine
				UK
				UK (Scotland)

For ease of comparison, Russia is mentioned at the beginning of the columns; states with multiple membership, are grouped together; the years cover time of Russia's membership.

competitive HE environments in CIS, SCO, EEU, and BRICS. This is even more true for further expansion of Russian HE in Africa, Southeast Asia and Latin America (Shenderova, 2016; Yousef, 2024; Labraña et al., 2024; Shenderova, 2025).

The Western boundaries of these regional spaces have become harder for Russian HE in Europe⁴ neighbouring with Russia. Since 2014, the EU announced the end of strategic partnership with Russia and imposed first sanctions closing opportunity to attract the EU funding for Russian universities except via the Jean Monnet Programme (Shenderova, 2020b). They, however, maintained opportunities to join their European partners in Erasmus+ actions and national funding of European states for mobility including within collaborative degrees (Deriglazova, 2025). The COVID-19 pandemic erected new barriers for EU-Russia internationalization. Closing the borders and significant cut of reasons for visa issuing stopped short-term mobility further added by mutual entry ban for users of Russian and European vaccines. Further, each EU country developed its own strategy for Russian vaccine recognition; constraints gradually relaxed (Shenderova et al., 2023). However, the Schengen visa issuing and entrance for research purposes were significantly hindered till mid-August 2022 due to multiplication of additional requirements. The pandemic visa restrictions have made entrance barriers hardly surmountable for majority of Russian academics since 2020 (Cai et al., 2022). The pandemic visa limitations were valid until mid-August 2022. They tightened in autumn 2022 due to the war varying from issuing visas for short-term visits in travel period to their full ban for Russian citizens.

Sanctions have snowballed since 26 February 2022, when Germany suspended all kinds of cooperation in HE and research with Russia, urging the EU to follow (O'Malley & Gardner, 2022). Regular updates of the EU sanction packages are documented (EC, 2025) and studied in the literature (Woodall, 2024; Lanko & Zotova, 2022; Brooks & Rensimer, 2024; Mäkinen, 2024; Suprun & Kivistö, 2025; Korkea-aho & Lonardo, 2025; Shenderova, 2025). Drawing of these sources, Table 7 summarizes the toughest sanctions impacted on Russian organizations and citizens including HEIs, student applicants and academics.

General and national sanctions excluded Russian HEIs from all EU/member states programmes of international and university collaborations including EU funded programmes of scientific collaborations (Horizon) and mobility (Erasmus +). They significantly limited an import of the equipment and software to Russian universities. The full suspension of international cooperation ended all collaborative degree programmes with European partners. Some Russian universities still mention these partnerships showing

Table 7
European sanctions affected Russian universities, student applicants and academics.

Type	General (EU)	National (European states)	Organizational (associations, agencies, businesses)	Institutional (universities)
Entry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited number of reasons to entry Europe - Increased time for visa processing - Extended list of documents for visa - Ban on entry for listed persons (e.g. the rectors of Russian universities publicly supported the war) - Suspension of simplification the visa processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full ban for academic visits via external borders (Czech Republic, Poland, and Finland) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full suspension of the rights of representation for Russia in the Bologna Follow-Up Group (EHEA) - Full suspension the rights of representation for all Russian quality assurance agencies European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA) - Ban for online access from Russia - Ban for access to job application services from Russia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extra processing and consideration of the applicant's documents - Rejection for the applicants of dual-use study programmes - Ban for online access to the websites from Russia
Finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ban for Russian bank accounts including SWIFT ban for money transfer - Freeze for bank accounts of Russian universities in the EU - Full suspension of funding for Russian universities within the EU scholarship programmes - Full suspension for reimbursement of travels to and from Russia 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rejection to open bank accounts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fee-based study only (for students) - Ban of reimbursement for travels to and from Russia
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full suspension of institutional cooperation - Ban of dual-use equipment and software to Russia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full suspension of cooperation agreements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full ban of MS Teams for Russian universities (Microsoft) - Times New Roman font is blocked for users from Russia and disappears in pdf files (Monotype) - Full suspension of accreditations and labelling (AACSB, AMBA, BGA, EFMD) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full suspension for cooperation with Russia-affiliated researchers - Termination of contracts for staff used university account remotely from Russia - Ban for university gadget usage in Russia

⁴ We use the term 'Europe', or 'European states' when we mean not only in the EU and its member states but also Norway, Switzerland and the UK. They are not the EU members but recent active partners of Russian universities.

themselves as desirable for European partners (SPbSU, 2025a; UrFU, 2025). In addition, the sanctions negatively affected Western researchers too, disrupting multiple long-term collaborations and even the areas of studies (Morris, 2023).

General sanctions provide a framework for national, organizational and institutional sanctions which vary significantly dependent on a vision of particular country or entity. For example, international quality assurance agencies chose different strategies. The agencies focused on business education, withdrew their accreditations from all Russia-based programmes (Forbes, 2022). Other Europe-based agencies which evaluated Russian programmes and universities (MusiQuE, Belgium; ZeVA, ACQUIN, FIBAA, evalag and ASIIN, all Germany), did not do it. Online libraries and journal databases have made their own decision: some of them (but not all) banned access of Russian universities or from Russia.

WURs still rate Russian universities. THE suspended the profiles described Russian universities but continue to rank them. QS suspended an extensive promotion of Russian universities. Currently, QS website bans an access from Russia but continues ranking Russian universities and providing basic information on each of them.

European research and HE associations follow different approaches to sanctions too. Research associations continue to invite Russia-affiliated researchers to Europe. However, associations aimed at impact in the sectors with institutional membership demonstrate tougher approach suspended membership for Russian universities, e.g. European University Association (EUA).

Some agencies of international education continue their presence in Russia (DAAD and L'Institut français) but other closed their offices (e.g. Institute of Finland). Individual scholarships are available for Russian citizens in an individual capacity but requests the end of affiliations with Russian universities. Scholar-at-risk funding is available for Russian citizens staying abroad only. The requirements of agencies supported scholars-at-risk regarding travels and publishing in Russia vary being not necessarily controlled in a coherent manner.

Western, including European, universities demonstrate the most significant spectrum of their sanction policies and their implications. They vary from total ban of online access to their websites and termination of contracts for Russia-located staff and students, to inviting Russia-affiliated researchers as co-authors and participants of scientific events. University sanctions policies are mostly flexible with regard to publications because their number impacts on university funding. The universities may forbid, permit or be indifferent regarding publications of their staff in Russia-affiliated journals including scholars at risk (which ideally should prevent their publication opportunities in Russia). The same is true for co-authorship with Russia-affiliated colleagues even if the latter publicly support the war.

Thus, the sanctions of 56 countries in total raised the costs of purchasing the equipment, mobility and knowledge exchange. This undermined a research and collaborative capacity for Russian HE, re-shaped some areas of study, and caused the radical shift of macro-focus of Russian internationalization policy from the Global North to the Global South (see Image 1).

Russia's leadership demonstrate bloc-like approach to confront the sanctions.⁵ Thus, the Government divides the modern world into 'friendly' countries which have not joined the sanction campaign, and the 'unfriendly' countries (GoR, 2022, Image 1). Russia regularly indicates willingness to restore cooperation immediately after sanctions cancelling (GoR, 2022; PoR, 2022; MFA, 2023; United Russia, 2025).

Within the country, Russia's leadership intimidates the population announcing a 'self-cleaning of Russian society' from 'the fifth column of the collective West and national-traitors' who are 'measuring everything and everyone by their own standards' (PoR, 2022). The laws on 'foreign agents' and 'undesirable organizations' criminalise representation or contacts with any foreign organization including visiting their websites (TASS, 2025b). The vague legislative definitions enable both targeted or mass repressions. Currently, the Russian state prefers a targeted approach. For example, paying a fee for membership in the Association of Slavic, Eastern European and Eurasian Studies (ASEEES), or for IELTS exams and certificates issued by British Council could bring to a holder a fine from €3000–5000 or imprisonment for funding these 'undesirable' organization. However, there is no punishment for the Valdai club speakers who have work or study experience in these or other 'undesirable' organizations and 'unfriendly' countries. Furthermore, study or research visits to the 'friendly' countries (e.g. China or Iran) could also be a reason for state treason accusations (NGS, 2023).

Thus, the sanctions made Western borders for regional spaces of Russian HE much less permeable than during the COVID-pandemic constraints but more permeable than the Iron Curtain. Five of EHEA member states (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Serbia, and Türkiye) have not joined the sanctions, and their universities continued cooperation with Russian partners. EHEA (2022) has not excluded Russia despite the request of Ukraine (Suprun & Kivistö, 2025).

The next sections analyse how regional spaces of Russian HE correspond with spatial imaginaries and internationalization policy.

4. Spatial imaginaries about Russian HE

This section explores spatial imaginaries of Russian HE as a mixture of reflections on Soviet educational strength and the experience gained from 40 years of cooperation with the West. We focus on the meaning of regional spaces for Russian HE in these spatial imaginaries traditionally focused on the West, as a reference point for partnership or competition since modelling the first university on Western European templates in the serfdom empire (Shenderova, 2020b). The communists imaged the whole world as a space of competition between capitalism and socialism. They promoted the USSR as 'a vanguard of progressive humankind' embodied by persons and states sympathized with socialist ideas. Subsequently, mass Soviet HE was a 'forge of personnel' and a role model for socialist-oriented economies (Katsakioris, 2019; Chankseliani, 2022; Shenderova et al., 2023). Therefore, occasional HE and research

⁵ The background of current Russia's leaders should be taken into account including their security service careers in the bloc-divided Cold War world and their experience of building and benefitting from a rent-extractive regime which they want to maintain.

Image 1. Russia and 56 'unfriendly countries'.
Source: [Shenderova \(2025\)](#).

Table 8

Policy justifications for regional places of Russian HE and internationalization activities within.

Regional space of HE	Policy justification	Internationalization activities
CIS	Common HE area based on common USSR legacy	Four Slavic universities ¹ (1990s) CIS Network university (2009)
EHEA	Creation of common European area for HE and research	Student, academic and administrative mobility, collaborative (including joint and double) degree programmes, joint research and publications (2003)
SCO	Development of integration processes in education, science and technologies	Network SCO university (2009) for exchanges and collaborative programmes in particular areas of study
BRICS	Facilitation of mutual recognition of qualifications, development of common standards for quality assurance, evaluation system and ranking	Network BRICS university also known as BRICS Universities League (2016) for development of collaborative degrees and short-term mobility
EEU	Creation the Common Eurasian Educational Area	Network EEU university (2022) for integration of HE systems, development and control of educational standards for online education, training programme development

Sources: websites of CIS, EHEA, SCO, BRICS+ EEU, PFUR, MGIMO, HSE.

¹ The Slavic (or Slavonic) universities are institutions located in Armenia, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan, jointly supervised by the Ministries responsible for HE of four CIS countries and Russia. See the details in [Shenderova \(2025\)](#).

cooperation with Western institutions was an arena of intersection the interests of academic, political and economic elites on both the socialist and capitalist sides. The regional spaces of Russian HE, shaped on the splinters of the USSR and socialist system, have received new official justifications of their cross-border and transcontinental integration initiatives (see [Table 8](#)).

These policy justifications could be considered in alignment with political rationales for internationalization ([Knight, 2004](#); [Balbachevsky et al., 2020](#); [Mäkinen, 2022](#)). In Russia, this aims to shape continental and cross-continental HE areas as alternatives to EHEA for global superiority of Russia. Based on the [Table 8](#). data, one could claim that this political rationale has shaped the spatial imaginaries of Russian HE for EHEA, CIS, EEU, SCO, and BRICS, as follows.

EHEA membership fuelled spatial imaginary of Russia as part of Broader Europe, the West, and the Global North. European branding provided a chance to overcome the old trauma of isolation and catch-up development ([Marquand & Scott, 2018](#); [Gromyko, 2019](#); [Balbachevsky et al., 2020](#)). Spatial imaginaries of Russian HE in CIS, EEU, BRICS, and SCO can also be said to epitomize resentment in terms of focussing on the role of Russian universities as the core and reference for socialist HE system, the loss of which is regretted and resented. Thus, Russia continues the Soviet discourse presenting itself as a unifier for CIS and EEU that implies Moscow as the neoimperium intellectual core ([Miller, 2025](#)). Russia's claims on leadership in SCO and BRICS as a 'vanguard of Global Majority' ([Karaganov et al., 2023:6](#)) literally reproduce the Soviet discourse but cynically substitute a dedication to socialist principles with a stance of non-alignment with sanctions ([Trenin, 2023](#)).

However, unlike the Soviet era, Russia's scientific identity and global positioning appeal to the past without unity. Russia is imagined as a sole 'state-civilization' ([MFA, 2023](#); [Mezhuev, 2022](#); [Timofeev, 2023](#)) which 'absorbed the political model of Genghis Khan's great Mongol empire' ([Karaganov, 2025](#)). After several about turns in values, now Russia is promoted as a global defender of

'traditional values' for the Global South (Karaganov et al., 2023; Valdai club report, 2024). Such neoimperialistic literature reproduces a century-old discourse of British colonial administration used by the vice-Roy of India (Lord Curzon, 1910) discussing 'turn' or 'pivot to the East' (Valdai club report, 2019; Kolosov & Zotova, 2023). This arguably reduces trust for Russia's initiatives amongst post-colonial countries and ignores leading ambitions of China (CPPCC National Committee, 2024) backed by much more solid financial support (Reuters, 2025).

Regional priorities of Russia's partnerships also vary significantly. The impact of the West on Russia and its HE is lauded or demonized but still recognised as a reference point. Russia's leadership has changed its views from advocating Russia as the 'largest European nation' (PoR, 2005; RIA Novosti 2018) to viewing 'most European states' as 'creating threats to the security and sovereignty of Russia' (cited in MFA, 2023; see also PoR, 2021; 2024a). MFA (2023) prioritizes CIS, EEU, SCO and BRICS while the textbook 'Basics of Russian statehood'⁶ (2024: 403) focuses on BRICS, OPEC+, Africa and Latin America as 'non-Western world'. Libman & Sokolov (2025) consider Russia as a 'non-Western country [...] confronted with the import of Western economics ideas.' They see this import as internationalization of ideas, and 'public intellectuals' as their 'translators' who enabled 'to discredit it [the regime] in the eyes of the wider public' with the usage of media. Patrushev also believes that the West uses controlled media to discredit the political leaders, institutes of the state power and Russian spiritual-moral values for further dictating Russian society another values and models of development (AIF, 2020). Chirikov and Fedyukin (2021) see maintaining Westernization of Russian HE as the only way 'to regain global influence'. Naryshkin (2022) promotes a rejection of the 'Bologna system' as a way to develop Russian HE independently. The 'liberal' respondents of Pavlova (2025) think that Russia is not a part of Europe. Zavadskaya and Gerber (2023) maintain the end of social science in Russia which 'flourished' in a few universities with 'intellectual support from social scientists in the West' before 2022. The proponents of Western or 'non-Western' focusses similarly propagate unification of future common educational standards more than their flexibility. The only difference between is the question of which standards should be used for unification: European/-international (Chirikov & Fedyukin, 2021; Kuzminov & Yudkevich, 2022) or self-developed/based on unique Soviet traditions (Sadovnichiy, 2024; TASS, 2024). They also demonstrate similar commitment to university rankings (QS and MosIUR) and Western-developed quantitative indicators.

All stakeholders of internationalization policy have common spatial imaginary of Russian HE system as one amongst globally competitive leaders in internationalization and uncontested leader in CIS and EEU. Regardless, such rhetorics do not clarify the concrete benefits for universities, academics and students in the regional spaces of Russian HE.

These controversial spatial imaginaries have provided similarly controversial criteria for internationalization policy performance since the President of Russia announced 'competitiveness enhancement' (PoR, 2012). This has fuelled data extractivism because the focus of internationalization policy on quantitative indicators. Their achievement is seen as Russia's ability to compete with the Western countries in accordance with criteria mainly developed in the West. 5–100 aimed at the entry of at least 5 Russian universities to the top-100 of any WUR. The national goals related to internationalization of HE comprise Russia entering into the league of the 10 globally leading countries in volume of research and development (GoR, 2023, Annex 1; PoR 2024a; 2024b). This indicator calculates a growth of share for Russia-affiliated publications indexed in WoS and Scopus databases. Furthermore, an achievement of national goals in science and education is mechanically calculated as the average position of Russian universities in top-500 of QS, THE, ARWU and MosIUR (Gershman et al., 2025: 121, 125 – 126). In turn, ranking expansion requires an increase in international students studying in Russia. In 2017, MoSHE announced their growth to 750,000 by 2020 (Interfax, 2017b). Current documents foresee 500,000 international students in Russian HEIs by 2030 including those who study in the branch campuses abroad (PoR, 2024b; Basics of Russian statehood, 2024: 349). Other goals for Russian HE system have included increase of international academics, income generation due to educational export and attraction of fee-based students, and intervention to global informal academic networks of contacts and national security (PoR, 2012; Volkov & Melnyk, 2019; Crowley-Vigneau et al., 2021).

The proponents of 'competitiveness enhancement' promoted the invitation of Western academics as key to the success of internationalization due to increase the numbers of highly-cited publications (Marginson, 2014; Kuzminov & Yudkevich, 2022). This line is continued in warring Russia. Many international academics having left Russia or withdrew their affiliations obeying the sanctions policies. But Russian universities are particularly proud to host 69 academics and experts from the EU and USA (Minobrnauki, 2024) despite the lack of frequency of their appearance in the classrooms (Shenderova, 2025).⁷

Despite a failure of 5–100 attempts to enter the top-100 of any WUR, along with further tightening of the Western boundaries for Russian HE due to the sanctions, Russia has maintained the Western focus of internationalization policy performance. Gershman et al. (2025) describes in detail the lists of countries and international rankings used for developing indicators for Russian HE and science: the Western countries and rankings prevail. Thus, since the 1990s, Russia's HE reforms and internationalization policy continue to rely on foreign approaches, criteria and countries the majority of which are concentrated in the West, and particularly, Europe.

Thus, spatial imaginaries of Russian HE, are fuelled by (1) traditional ambitions to become a part of global/European/Eurasian science community for security reasons; (2) the intention to commercialize an imagined global nostalgia about the attractiveness of the Russian core of the Soviet HE system to decrease the state's financial obligations within the country; (3) resentment as an expression of

⁶ 'The Basics of Russian statehood' (2024) is a textbook for the eponymous one-semester course. It is coercively included into curricula of any bachelor and specialist degree programme taught in each Russian HEIs as obligatory for studying by all students of Russian universities since 2024. The authors of this book have educational background in military, hard and children pedagogy studies. The leading author serves in the PA. The book is published by RANEPa Presidential Academy where the second author serves as a vice-rector. The third author works at MSU.

⁷ Remarkably, the former Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Austria is entrusted to study Russia's key issues at SPbSU (2025b), which is *alma mater* for President Putin.

angst about the loss of superpower status which utilized mass Soviet HE as a window of socialism. For decades, the global ambitions of Russian politicum and academia unanimously inspire policy request to collaborate or compete with ‘highly-ranked’ universities and ‘highly-cited scholars’ mainly located in the West. Ambitions in geopolitics presumably inspires promoting cooperation with the regional spaces where Russian HE is not represented by sustainable cross-border internationalization initiatives, like Africa and Latin America. Neoimperial imaginaries prioritize promotion of Russian HE in CIS and EEU. Thus, controversial spatial imaginaries multiply geographic focuses while funding is given for competition and/or cooperation with the world HE leaders because the global ambitions prevail.

The next section unveils how the Russia’s leadership appoints the leaders of Russian HE who justify these spatial imaginaries developing internationalization policy.

5. Privileges as the shadows of Russia’s internationalization policy

This section addresses the privileged internationalization. It is understood as a set of decision-making processes deliberately built to provide the rent extraction for insiders in internationalization policy as a linchpin of neoliberal reforms. Develop the concept of shadows in internationalization (Shenderova et al., 2024), we unveil how privileged internationalization in Russia has led to such dark-side effects as ‘neocoloniality’ of Russian HE within and outside the country.

Shaping privileged internationalization, Russia’s leadership has drawn upon the Soviet traditions of particularly limited access to information and contacts with ‘abroad’. Ideological and security concerns caused the strictest control by the Party and security services for all research related to the West, and particularly in social sciences (Pallot in Kangas et al., 2023). The Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (CC CPSU) supervised their studies and supervision in Moscow, and to a lesser extent, in Leningrad in a limited number of think tanks. They comprised research institutions, the main campus of the Higher Party School network, and few university departments responsible for ideological courses⁸. These institutions explored Western experience looking for ways to galvanize the decaying socialist system while sustaining privileges for *nomenklatura* insiders.⁹ The Party and security services approved a set of privileges for these institutions including access to information, contacts and teaching of foreigners with more comfortable time norms for research and teaching workload in comparison with other Russian HEIs¹⁰ (Shenderova, 2011).

The institutional fabric of Russian HE reproduces Soviet inequalities in allocation of access and funding for international activities. Two super-privileged Muscovite institutions are supervised and funded by the Government and PA, namely, HSE and Presidential Academy RANEPa. Since 1992, both institutions have incorporated the core staff and premises from the Soviet privileged institutions mentioned above including Moscow office of the Higher Party School. The current role of HSE and RANEPa in internationalization policy demonstrates an extreme extent of monopolization opportunities in Russian HE sector to impact on policy development and data extraction.

HSE has become a polygon for testing the ‘competitiveness enhancement’ approach’ since the Government approved the HSE Development Programme in 2008. HSE is first Russian university obliged (1) to be comparable with ‘leading education and research centres of social-economic profile from abroad’ (GoR, 2008); (2) ‘impacting on the global agenda’ integrating its personnel with the Western centres and (3) collaborating with their researchers for the purposes of increase the number of publications in highly-cited journals (MoSHE, 2009). The Government supports RANEPa since 2012 for entering to leading global rankings and obtaining international accreditations (GoR, 2012).

Special government funding and comfort teaching workload provided HSE and RANEPa Moscow staff working conditions amenable to facilitating international and media visibility. In addition, selected academics have opportunities for additional earnings in ‘independent’ Moscow School of Social and Economics Sciences (MSSES, or *Shaninka*) and based in RANEPa premises, MGIMO university advising MFA, and private New Economic School (NES) advising PA and MoSHE. The selected colleagues from St. Petersburg branches of RANEPa and HSE combined their work with duties at one of the most expensive and well-funded division of SPbSU, Faculty of Liberal Arts and Sciences (Smolny Institute), and an ‘independent’ European University in St. Petersburg (EUSP). Some of these academics also simultaneously worked abroad even after the sanction policies directly prohibited their staff to work in Russian institutions.

Therefore, belonging to a narrow circle of academics signalled an expansion in their opportunities to earn money and represent themselves as members of an international scholarly community. In addition, a network of a few institutions has gained a particular access to government funding for internationalization policy development and support measures. HSE, RANEPa, EUSP, NES, School of Advanced Sciences (SAS) at the University of Tyumen’, had close mutual ties with organisations which administrated, evaluated and trained university managers during ‘competitiveness enhancement’ within 5–100. These are the operators of the state programmes, namely, state organisation ‘Sociocenter’, and private business school Skolkovo responsible for the assessment of 5–100 participants (Shenderova, 2018a). For example, EUSP (2016) received project funding of ‘Sociocenter’ for data gathering and seminars in

⁸ Ideological courses in CPSU history, Marxist-Leninist Philosophy and political economy were the integral parts of any degree programme and studied in the elite faculties responsible for the development, justification and dissemination of the Party line in any aspect of the Soviet life.

⁹ *Nomenklatura* comprised the lists of institutions and persons approved by the Communist Party for their special access to commodities, services, and opportunities unavailable for ordinary Soviet people. The privileges could be given or taken by adding or exclusion of the lists (Ledeneva, 2013, pp. 19-49; Matthews, 2011).

¹⁰ The USSR had 911 HEIs in all 15 republics. 339 had the right to study international students. The Russian Socialist Federative Socialist republic (RSFSR) had 514 HEIs, and 175 of them taught international students. (Arefyev and Sheregi, 2014: 12).

university governance for university administrators participated in 5–100. 5–100 universities were obliged to train their personnel in Skolkovo at the expenses of their funding for internationalization (Chirikov, 2023).¹¹

These institutions are presented as ‘pockets of efficiency’ (Gel'man 2021; Zavadskaya & Gerber, 2023), where faculty enjoy salaries at Western European level, academic freedom ‘in a relative extent’ (Dubrovsky, 2017), and ‘special rules within a special academic zone’ (Volkov & Melnyk, 2019)¹² in exchange of their success in internationalization (Dubrovsky & Kaczmarska, 2021).

One could maintain that promotion of these closely-tied privileged institutions as ‘pockets of efficiency’ justify regional, sectoral and university disparities in Russian HE in the course of neoliberal reforms. Firstly, labelling these few institutions as ‘efficient’ without clear definition of efficiency criteria, masks the explosion in management bloat: the numbers of vice-rectors reached 20 in HSE and SPbSU since 2010 (Shenderova, 2011). The current rectors of MSU, SPbSU, ITMO, and recent rectos of HSE and RANEPa along with some of their deputies have occupied their positions for decades. This is much far from Western standards of effective university management.

Second, the idea of elite universities as islands of good practices normalizes the idea of academic freedom as a privilege. Focusing academic freedom on opinion expressing, ignores the structural limitations for academic freedom preventing its rooting, such as control-oriented state accreditation, sweatshop workload, and deficit of internationalization opportunities at the sectoral level.

Third, claims about own correspondence with Western criteria justify the reform development and data extractivism as a privilege. HSE, RANEPa, Skolkovo and Sociocenter simultaneously developed neoliberal reforms, criteria for internationalization policy, and gathered data on policy implementation from 5–100 participants. Gathered data presented Russia in international projects, increasing visibility of their developers for the President and globally (HSE, 2019; 2025).¹³

Thus, one could claim that privileged universities and think tanks could share responsibility with the key stakeholders of Russian internationalization policies for data extractivism, uneven allocation of government funding and hindering academic freedom in Russian HE in general. Privileged internationalization as a pillar for neoliberal HE reforms has not addressed traditionally stark regional imbalances in access to international knowledge and internationalization opportunities. This led for example, to large disparities in actual remuneration, hidden by formally equal salaries in state universities located in different regions, and between the employees within single universities as well (Shenderova, 2020b, 2023). With the equal requirements to outcoming mobility with the leading world HE centres in Europe, USA and Australia, internationalization brought a particular burden on Ural, Siberian and Far Eastern universities which had to spend much more due to the distances (Uzhegova & Baik, 2022). Thus, internationalization policy has exacerbated inequality and introduced ‘coloniality’ within domestic regional space of Russian HE.

To summarize, the privileged universities have made quantitative criteria have become a common point of Western and Russian neoliberal reforms and mutual cooperation. The decision-making processes of selection for international activities as a marker of privileges at institutional level are almost unchanged since Soviet times. However, privileged internationalization based on quantitative criteria represents a form of shadow inequalities, among multiple other forms, which have been invisible to international funding programmes and partners while Russian universities provided them the prominent numbers of incoming students and academics (Shenderova, 2018b, 2023).

The next sections explore how implementation of internationalization policy based on privileges and quantitative criteria, have conflicted with the spatial imaginaries and regional spaces of Russian HE.

6. Policy implementation I: spatial imaginaries and internationalization activities in HE

The spatial imaginaries of Russian HE do not take into account the realities of internationalization policy implementation where universities operate at home and abroad. First, regulation of the degree programmes in Russia at national and university level is rigid and control-oriented that prevent the improvement of the degree programmes content. University administrators often interpret policy document in their own manner significantly intervening into curricula design (Shenderova, 2023, 2025). In addition, multiple data requests have been time-consuming and not necessarily paid for when academics reported on their internationalization activities (Ustyuzhantseva et al., 2020; Shenderova, 2020a). Second, while Russia lost an interest to research collaboration in the ‘near abroad’, the latter develop own flagship universities also welcoming international branch campuses and joint universities including built in partnership with the Western leaders (Shenderova, 2016; Ubaydullaeva, 2020; Kuzhabekova, 2024).

Third, both policymakers and universities demonstrate neocolonial thinking. Russian universities have taken CIS students for granted the idea that they always strive to study in Russia and according to local quality standards (Shenderova, 2025). By 2020, 75,2 % of international students arrived from CIS countries (Shenderova, 2020b). Their recruitment fulfilled internationalization KPIs for reporting purposes without requiring university administrators to countenance unconventional solutions. This disproportion in

¹¹ The trainer team included Skolkovo professor who simultaneously served as a Deputy Chair of the Council for Competitiveness Enhancement evaluated 5-100 success (Skolkovo, 2025) and academics of RANEPa, HSE and/or SAS Tymen’.

¹² Remarkably, that the promoters of internationalisation policy use for the privileged universities the word “zone” [zona in Russian] which is also informally uses in relation to the prisoner camps in penitentiary system including the special camps where the imprisoned scientists were involved into nuclear weapon development under the supervision of security services in the middle of 20 century.

¹³ HSE rector in 1992-2021, and its current academic supervisor, presented 5-100 results gathered from the whole sector, for the President of Russia (PoR, 2017). Alexey Kudrin who has worked with Putin since the 1990s and defended his doctoral thesis in RANEPa (2019), was the founder of EUSP, Dean of the Smolny Institute (2011-2022) and the Chair of the Accounting Chamber of Russia responsible for assessment of the 5-100 results for the Government and President.

international student enrolment between the ‘near’ and ‘far’ abroad has conflicted with the spatial imaginaries concerning the global attractiveness of Russian HE. The reform developers have pressured Russian HEIs to collaborate with the ‘world leading universities’ of the Global North ranked in the top –500 (or even top-300) and attracting their international students (Shenderova, 2018a, 2020a,b; Gurko et al., 2019), or any other students from ‘far abroad’ with a lack of support for CIS student recruitment and domestic degree programmes in Russian where they studied. Therefore, both Russia’s leadership and universities have considered regional spaces of the Global South and nearest neighbourhood as the sources of international students but avoided focusing research partnerships there. As a result, the racing for international students from outside the CIS has shaped a perception of Russian universities as cheap degree providers with modest entrance criteria. This is evidenced in an opinion poll of Egyptian students (Roscongress, 2022).

Fourth, Russian universities demonstrate limited ability to integrate with national HE systems in prioritized regional spaces. For example, the Slavic universities under the CIS auspices do not harmonize and integrate ‘Russian’ and ‘local’ curricula implementing them in total separation (Shenderova, 2025). Remarkably, widely advertised network universities within CIS, EEU, SCO and BRICS finally has become an additional tool to strengthen the international student recruitment to full-time study on the degree programmes in Russian. The courses of foreign universities are hardly (if any) incorporated into Russian curricula (Shenderova, 2023, 2025). The rigidity of quality assurance standards at national and university level has led to the abandoning of SCO University’s original aim to issue its own degree certificate together with the certificates of partner universities (SCO, 2025). The Network BRICS University have a limited number of international students (PFUR, 2024), offering them mainly short-term mobility including seasonal schools, separate modules or courses (HSE, 2024). Focusing on habitual Russian-speaking programmes and courses, Russian universities invariably cut their internationalization opportunities to CIS/EEU regional spaces, in comparison with global and local leaders operated there.

All this is applicable for all internationalization activities prioritized by Russia’s leadership, including the recruitment of international students for degree programmes in Russia, number of the degree programmes in English, collaborative degrees often presented as double or joint; massive open online courses (MOOCs); opening branch campuses of Russian universities abroad, network universities, and joint universities.

The most recent student recruitment to study in Russia full-time comprises 250,557 students in 2023, that is lower than pre-pandemic enrolment of 278,596 students in 2019. The structure for countries of origin also changed in comparison with pre-pandemic 2019. The number of bachelor students admitted from Kazakhstan which has the largest border with Russia amongst other neighbouring countries, has fallen by two-thirds in 2023 comparison with 2019. In 2023 the students from Turkmenistan prevailed in bachelor student admission. Specialist degrees mainly focused on medicine and hard science, are popular amongst the students from India, Egypt and Iran. Meanwhile the numbers of students admitted from China to study at master programmes increased by a factor of two by 2023. The total number of international student admission for full-time bachelor studies in 2023 is 40,399 instead of 57,371 in 2019 (Shenderova, 2025). Thus, warring Russia as a study destination becomes less attractive for CIS students and that is particularly so for those arrived from Kazakhstan.

Russian universities provide a limited number of the degree programmes in English during 2025/2026 admission campaign (see Table 9).¹⁴

Since the sanctions ended all collaborative degree agreements with Western institutions, Russian universities have actively announce new collaborative degrees openings with partners in the Global South and near abroad. However, it is challenging to estimate their dynamics and total number due to a lack of collaborative degree definition in Russian law (Federal Law ‘On Education’, 2012). In addition, a novelty of these partnerships prevents to evaluate their sustainability.

The small number of MOOCs in English both at national and international platforms limits global visibility for Russian universities. 5–100 funded leading universities to develop MOOCs for US based platforms Coursera and edX ignoring domestic and Global Southern platforms. Their number reached 351 MOOCs by 2020 but only 11 % of these courses were in English, increasing from eight in 2017 to 39. The National Platform of Open Education opened.ru (NPOE) hosted 450 MOOCs in 2020 (URFU, 2020: 5). In spring 2022 edX and Coursera terminated cooperation (Skillbox.ru, 2022). NPOE became the main platform for Russian MOOCs. Their total number increased from 869 in 2022 to 1407 at present with number of MOOCs in English from ten to 100 dependently on study year season. Chinese platform XuetangX hosts 44 MOOCs of four Russian universities (Shenderova, 2025) amongst 11,196 online courses in total. Therefore, one could claim that since the end of 5–100 funding, Russian universities have not been active in running their MOOCs at international online platforms outside Russia.

By 2025, Russian universities opened 31 branches of five private and 26 state universities in Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus,

Table 9

Degree programmes available for international students in English and Russian in 2025.

Language	Bachelor	Specialist	Master	Aspirantura
Russian	6416	1003	4109	2888
English	11	3	28	7

Source: Education in Russia.com, 15.05.2025.

¹⁴ Education in Russia is an official website for the selection of foreign citizens to study in Russia. The programmes in other languages than Russian or English are not mentioned there.

Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Moldova, UAE (Dubai), Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan. These branches teach students in Russian in accordance with Russian quality standards, demonstrating limited ability to compete with other international branches in these countries, which work mainly in English.

Joint institutions including the Slavic universities and Sino-Russian university Shenzhen MSU-BIT (SMBU) do not integrate their Russian curricula with the programmes or courses implemented within these institutions in accordance with local quality standards in English or local languages. SMBU (2025) offers the only option of outcoming mobility (to MSU) and obtain its degree for additional fee. Not surprisingly, SMBU has to announce a supplementary enrolment to its master's degrees.¹⁵

Thus, spatial imaginaries of Russian HE as globally competitive are not supported by relevant changes in law, university regulation, and degree programme management contributing flexible integration with international partners and knowledge production in English. Russia's leadership perceives the progress in rankings as the proxies of excellence (Antonowicz et al., 2017). However, neoliberal reforms continue to cut basic funding for academic and administrative positions. It is enough to look at schedules at university websites to recognise that contact hours could achieve 40 h per week or even more. >50 % of the Russian degrees in economics are not able to develop their own manuals and textbooks at all (Teleshova, 2025). This is indirect evidence of chronic underfunding Russian universities hosted these popular programmes along with extremely unproductive overloading of their academics.

Rare universities have their own campuses in Russia with very modest living conditions.¹⁶ As a rule, the universities do not provide an equipped working space for many academics visit universities for lecturing only using their own emails and phones for professional communication without reimbursement. None of 40 world class campuses promised by 2030 is built yet (Shenderova, 2025). While Russia's leadership invents a spatial imaginary of Russian HE, the universities do what they are able. The leadership motivates universities and academics to report about internationalization activities much more than to develop their own degrees, courses and research. The same is true for publications indexed in international databases analysed in the section below.

7. Policy implementation II: article production and interest of Russia-affiliated authors to internationalization of HE

The requirement to increase the number of publications indexed by WoS and Scopus has significantly impacted the life of universities and academics. Internationalization in Russia is subordinated to the tasks of imitation for the sake of metrics much more than a genuine knowledge production based on intrinsic scientific investigative interest. Russian universities may spend government funding on publishing articles in predatory journals. For example, the Account Chamber (AC, 2021: 27) particularly stresses this for KFU but it is not the only case. The universities invite hyper-prolific researchers with over 60 papers per year (Ioannidis et al., 2024), including those found to be engaged in fraudulent practices e.g. PFUR (Oleksiyenko, 2022; Ansed, 2023, 2025).

Some universities invite international researchers already affiliated abroad. 'Multiple affiliations strategy' increases international visibility of these researchers and their hosts in the West and in Russia. The names of invited academic stars boost the numbers of internationally indexed publications for their Russian hosts but also their personal citation index. As a rule, international academics involved in research collaborations rarely taught Russian students or administered academic processes to the same extent as their unprivileged Russian colleagues. Multiple affiliations in Russia and abroad have boosted visibility of the selected Russian academics worked both abroad and in several Russian universities simultaneously. In addition, the holders of multiple Russian affiliations have often used their affiliations in private HEIs for international audience to hide their work in presidential universities but continue contributing their publication related KPIs. Writing articles related to internationalization of HE and its implementation in Russia and elsewhere give their authors a chance to become visible for the developers of the reforms for probable further involvement in privileged internationalization. To highlight themselves as the holders of grassroots process-knowledge, the authors often describe their experience in internationalization including data gathering in their universities. The mantras mentioned in the Introduction, appear in publications to demonstrate loyalty to the Russian state's priorities. According to this hypothesis we could expect growth in the numbers of articles on 'technological sovereignty' in the near future.

Our findings present the preliminary results of our study (Comai, 2025a-c) of the publications about the internationalization of HE and published in WoS and Scopus indexed journals. In so doing, we identified 2882 journal articles identified via WoS and available on OpenAlex. They include 51 articles with at least an author with a Russian affiliation, 2536 articles with no author with a Russian affiliation, and 295 articles where the affiliation is not available (or, in a small number of cases, the country of the affiliation is not available). Table 10 and Image 2 present the dynamics of WoS indexed publications related internationalization of HE worldwide and with Russian affiliations.

The total number of publications in the field published in Q1 and Q2 Scopus journals is 5526 including 289 publications where at least one author has been Russia-affiliated. Image 3 shows that Russia-affiliated authors increased the number of their publications in the topic by 2015 when the first results of 5–100 funding occurred, and achieved the maximum in 2021 when the 5–100 funding ended and the universities had to provide their final reports. The further decrease of publications in 2022 did not necessarily reflect sanctions impacts because such policy was only implemented later and many journals continue publishing Russia-affiliated authors (Mäkinen 2024; Lanko & Zotova, 2022). We assume that the number of Russia-affiliated publications decreased and because the funding for internationalization stopped but much less because of sanctions.

Two trends are immediately apparent: globally, publications about on of HE are growing despite geopolitical changes, whilst in

¹⁵ This happens in Guangdong province hosted >50 HEIs including several Sino-foreign universities with highly ranked international partners.

¹⁶ In the most European city of Russia, St. Petersburg, the way from student dormitories to study buildings could take almost two hours by public transport; heating in the student dormitories could be offered an option in the city where frosts reach 30°C (SPbPU, 2025).

Table 10
Dynamics of publications about internationalization of HE (WoS).

Publication year	No Russian affiliation	Russian affiliation	Affiliation N/A	Total	Russian affiliation share
2011	81	1	25	107	0.06 %
2012	104	2	24	130	0.13 %
2013	123	0	45	168	0.00 %
2014	85	1	48	134	0.06 %
2015	87	5	58	150	0.32 %
2016	75	1	42	118	0.06 %
2017	104	2	59	165	0.13 %
2018	95	7	50	152	0.44 %
2019	113	9	50	172	0.57 %
2020	143	11	75	229	0.70 %
2021	177	17	40	234	1.08 %
2022	138	7	46	191	0.44 %
2023	125	10	31	166	0.63 %
2024	55	2	32	89	0.13 %
Total	1505	75	625	2205	—

Number of publications about internationalisation of higher education
Counting relevant journal publications identified by Web of Science
Affiliation attributed based on OpenAlex data

* 'Russian affiliation' attributed if at least one author is affiliated with a Russia-based institution
Not included when affiliation is not available or could not be attributed to any country.

Image 2. Number of publications about internationalization of HE (WoS).

Russia they have been decreasing. We conclude that the global science demonstrates sustainable growth of research interest in internationalization as a phenomenon but Russian science demonstrates temporary interest in this field as a fashionable topic and as long as studies in the field are funded well.

Table 11 and 12 confirm concentration of the mostly cited publications in Moscow. The disparity in citations of publications with affiliation of HSE and other universities by a factor of nearly three is probably due to HSE available international ‘academic star’ recruitment.

The data confirm the high level of concentration the resources of the sector around Moscow where the research output and citation of HSE significantly exceed those produced by other institutions. Only two universities are located outside Moscow. Table 11 and 12 show a lack of publications in ‘independent’ HEIs presented as ‘successful’ in the policy literature including those funded for training of 5–100 participants.

Unlike the universities failed in intervention to top-100 of WURs chosen for references (except domestic MosIUR), their privileged academics and top-managers responsible have demonstrated personal success in their own integration into global academia. They have

Number of publications about internationalisation of higher education Counting relevant social sciences publications in Scopus-indexed journals

* 'Russian affiliation' attributed if at least one author is affiliated with a Russia-based institution

Image 3. Number publications about internationalization of HE (Scopus).

Table 11

Top-5 Russian HEIs on the numbers of publications in internationalization of HE (Scopus).

Number of publications	Cited	University, name	Location
8	82	HSE	Moscow
5	34	PFUR	Moscow
4	28	UrFU	Yekaterinburg
4	26	RANEPA	Moscow
5	23	MGIMO	Moscow

Table 12

Top-5 Russian HEIs on the numbers of publications in internationalization of HE (WoS).

Number of publications	Cited	University, name	Location
7	102	HSE	Moscow
7	19	MGIMO	Moscow
6	21	UrFU	Yekaterinburg
5	7	National Research Tomsk State University	Tomsk
4	13	SPbSU	St. Petersburg

become a prolific authors of publications co-authored with subordinates and based the data extracted from 5–100 participants and HE sector in general because of their role in policy evaluation and data extractivism. Many of these privileged persons including at least six HSE vice-rectors have been able to leave Russia since the outbreak of war. They smoothly overcame probable obstacles to their exit in Russia, landing in the US, UK and EU universities where some already had existing contacts. Visa and banking restrictions mentioned above, did not prevent privileged academics entering Europe urgently in spring 2022 or ‘evacuating’ family to Dubai (UAE) for further well-prepared ‘exile’ in Europe (Greenfield, 2023; Zayakin, 2022).

The ‘pro-Western’ ‘liberal’ orientation of a few institutions and their selected representatives together with their commitment to the Bologna principles and European values did not stop them from following practices far from contributing to greater equity in their own

country. These universities have built their international reputation on the bones of the chronically underfunded Russian HE system.

8. Conclusion: A capercaillie syndrome

The concepts of regional spaces and spatial imaginaries help to deepen understanding of boundaries for expansion for HE systems of democratic and authoritarian countries. A juxtaposition of regional spaces and spatial imaginaries enables to recognise how realistic is the internationalization policy, and how it could be improved. The countries and regional spaces where universities are the key stakeholders of internationalization policies, shape spatial imaginaries on their HE at least by listening to the universities' opinions. However, Russia's leadership frame internationalization policy by itself also involving a few privileged institutions into policy development and assessment. HSE and RANEPa as appointed leaders of Russian HE develop internationalization policy without sacrificing their principles of patron-clientelism and informal governance at the expense of any genuine internationalization beyond publication metrics and student numbers. These are the stakeholders of Russia's internationalization policy who perceive a rest of university community and academia as subordinated objects of extracting the data and translated discourses agreed with stakeholders' global ambitions.

Spatial imaginaries of Russia's HE see Russia as a prominent up-coming global player, the leading intellectual voice equal to China, in the Global South, and the first in the 'near abroad'. Organizing BRICS, SCO, CIS and EEU as regional spaces alternative for EHEA, Russian HE is able to compete with the West due to leading universities' intervention into the highest positions in WURs. However, these visions are far from the realities which Russian universities face during internationalization policy implementation at home and abroad.

Attempting to satisfy their global ambition, a conglomerate of closely-tied politics and academics behave like capercaillie males. These birds are so passionate about representing themselves that they sing their song for females but are not able to see what happens around them. Without feedback from the university community, the stakeholders produce spatial imaginaries controversial within themselves simultaneously prioritizing collaborations with the leading universities 'far abroad' and 'near abroad'. Unprecedented sanctions of the Global North countries including a majority of EHEA member have not changed the main focus of Russia's internationalization policy from 'far abroad' to 'near abroad' and inside the country making the Western boundaries of Russian HE less permeable for knowledge exchange and mobility. Furthermore, global ambitions in spatial imaginaries and hope to compete with the West by Western means have fuelled neoliberal reforms, and strengthened quantitative view on internationalization as their pillar. The developers of internationalization policy continue measuring national HE by Western quantitative standards avoiding rooting Western principles of governance in HE.

A perception of WURs as proxies of quality is not a solely Russian phenomenon: for example, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Saudi Arabia, and Singapore have implemented their HE reforms through internationalization directly or indirectly using similar criteria. But the Gulf states take into account the rankings but prioritize the improvement of national quality assurance systems also opening the doors for foreign universities and international branch campuses (Bailey & Purington, 2025). Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan have limited ability to support their HE systems focusing on building few new flagship universities only. They also provide opportunities to open branch campuses and joint universities, unlike Russia. Southeastern countries including those following the socialist way, have focused their internationalization on collaborative degree programmes and MOOCs (Aprimadya et al., 2025). Latin American and, in less extent, African universities not necessarily are focused on rankings acting in societies with extreme level of social-economic inequality and poverty (Pillay et al., 2023).

The Russian specificity is that spatial imaginaries about HE are developed in separation from realities of national quality assurance system and internationalization policy implementation. This performs spatial imaginaries from a strategic tool to rhetoric construction which however impact on policy implementation criteria. Policymakers and privileged academics ignore the competitive environments in CIS, EEU, SCO, and BRICS. Furthermore, spatial imaginaries of Russian HE demonstrates a neocolonial trend: research cooperation is focused on 'highly-ranked' partners far from regional spaces of Russian HE, with CIS, EEU, SCO and BRICS countries are perceived as the merely sources for international student enrolment. However, Russian universities build new partnerships with reputation of unreliable partners who change the focus of partnerships severing the links. This is the most significant effect of war and sanctions which will have a long-term impact.

The privileged internationalization monopolized opportunities for academic elites and strengthened imperialistic trend in spatial imaginaries giving a rise a 'coloniality' within the country. This not only have sapped Russian HE in general, but exacerbated inequalities at the regional, sectoral, and university level. Policy implementation inspired by imperial spatial imaginaries, undermines the unity of HE within Russia: while a majority of universities are deprived of the elementary conditions for domestic students and academics, the chosen few enjoy international representation.

Neoperial spatial imaginaries do not take into account that the restoration of capitalism made Russian HE one amongst many capitalist systems which prospective partners and students compare. In this comparison, Russian universities are not proactive in flexible developing modern internationalization activities. This is caused by rigid quality assurance procedures at national and university level, interventions of educational administrators into curricula design, and continued cut of funding for academic and administrative positions outside special government programmes. Russian universities focus their internationalization around Russian-language programmes, national quality assurance standards and traditions of micromanagement. Internationalization activities of Russian universities and their studies of Russian academia are not sustainable. They end soon after the end of their funding. Internationalization at home is not in focus of policy documents and related publications of Russia-affiliated academics.

180-turn of regional priorities has not changed principles of funding distribution and policy assessment. Russian politics, experts and academia in elite institutions produce the spatial imaginaries of Russian HE without engaging with the majority of Russian

universities responsible in dialogue on policy implementation. The place of Russian HE in the world is determined by calculating Western-developed quantitative indicators. Like capercaillies, the elites disseminate their imaginaries about Russian HE while avoiding to listen to domestic universities and ignoring realities of policy implementation in Russia and abroad. Thus, Russian HE is in limbo between Western-obsessed imaginaries and domestic limitations.

We recognise limitations for current and future research of positioning HE systems in the world. They comprise a specific of definitions for some internationalization activities in national legislation, different approaches for calculation numbers of international students and academics, and specific of national statistics. Sensitivity of personal data make it difficult to estimate the numbers of academic and student migration that is particularly true for processes involved authoritarian countries tend to repress for the links with 'unfriendly countries'. Fastly updated sensitive data hinder an assessment of the sanction impact on Russian HE and academia.

Russia is an extreme case which demonstrates what happens when the state and reform developers do not want to listen universities implementing their imaginaries at grass-root level. Both the state servants and privileged academics feel entitled to pressure universities for data extraction, purchasing trainings and textbooks not necessarily connected with the degree programme content. Meanwhile Russian universities are chronically underfunded; a majority of Russian academics work as 'translators' in sweatshop system having weak chances for developing new courses, research and internationalization activities. Recent developments in the USA and UK show that even the HE systems well-known as democratic, are not guaranteed from similar turn of event when the state aims to shoulder the financial burden, intervening into everyday university life, and leading academic experts choose opportunistic behaviour instead of uphold the principles of quality education for all.

Future research could use theoretical framework of this article to analyse the shadows in internationalization in the course of neoliberal reforms. In addition, this article provides a set of useful tools and insights for studying formal and informal networks of politics, academics and experts shaped by internationalization and impacted on its implementation in different regional spaces of HE and globally.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Svetlana Shenderova: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jeremy Morris:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Giorgio Comai:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Data curation, Methodology.

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